

Enhancing energy density of existing sensible thermal storage system with encapsulated PCM

Rok Koželj, Peter Kolar, Eva Zavrl, Damjan Klobčar, Uroš Stritih, Rok Stropnik*

¹University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Aškerčeva 6, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

Introduction: In the past decades many types of research have been done on PCMs for thermal storage in building's systems for use in new or existing building applications [1]. According to the European Technology Platform on Renewable Heating and Cooling further research on mechanisms of integrating PCMs into existing heating and cooling systems is one of the priorities for research on latent thermal storage. Furthermore, the emphasis is given to encapsulation and stabilisation of PCMs, in particular of salt-hydrates, which are cheaper than paraffin and does not present the fire risk [2]. He et al. experimentally investigated the performance of a water thermal storage tank with a packed bed of encapsulated paraffin wax. The 0.75 m³ water storage tank was filled with encapsulated PCMs with phase change temperature at around 68°C. During the 37°C/70°C discharging process the duration of outlet temperature from the thermal storage tank above 67°C is extended by 18% at the low flow rates in comparison to water thermal storage tank [3]. Zhou et al. investigated a centralized solar hot water system for residential buildings with spherically encapsulated paraffin wax with a phase change temperature of 60°C. The average solar fraction of a system without PCM was 51% while it increases to 80% when using PCM [4]. Compared to water heat storage tank, researches on encapsulated PCMs inside water heat storage tank are limited and most of them are numerical simulations instead of the experimental study [3]. The researches on water thermal storage tank with encapsulated PCMs are also mainly done for a heating system with an operational temperature above 40°C or for below 0°C. Therefore, the need for experimental research of a centralized latent thermal storage system for low-temperature heating or high-temperature cooling system for residential buildings is needed in a way to provide practical improvement of the energy density of existing water thermal storage system. The latter is especially needed in retrofits of residential buildings due to the RES system integration, where higher volumes of water thermal storage are needed in order to level out the mismatch between supply and demand [5]. Therefore the objective of the present research is to enhance the energy density of the existing water thermal storage system by integrating encapsulated PCM (salt-hydrate mixture) and experimentally investigate its performance for usage in low-temperature heating systems.

Materials and Methods: The system consisted of three 100 litres tanks connected in series where encapsulated PCMs were inserted inside each tank. PCM was encapsulated in spherical modules made of high-density polyethylene (HDPE) with a diameter of 80 mm. Inside each tank, 192 spheres were inserted what represented 31 litres of PCM in one tank and 576 spheres and 93 l of PCM in the whole system. This represents 37 % of PCM according to the total thermal storage volume. PCM that was used in the research was a salt-hydrate mixture with phase change temperature around 25°C with melting enthalpy of 271 kJ/l and specific enthalpy of 300 kJ/l in the range of 15 K. At first measurements with only water as a thermal storage medium were carried out and afterwards measurements with the inclusion of PCM capsules inside the water tanks were carried out. Water temperatures were measured at the bottom, middle and top of each tank and at the inlet and outlet of the thermal storage system. The water flow rate was measured at the inlet of the system and was set to be constant during the experiment. In both cases, operational conditions were the same. The thermal storage system was heated on 35°C and discharged with an inlet water temperature of 15°C to the final temperature of 17°C. Discharged heat from both systems was calculated and compared.

Results: At discharging process of heat from 35°C to 17°C, the discharged heat from the thermal storage system was 7.6 kWh and 12.8 kWh for the water thermal storage system and latent thermal storage system respectively. This result shows that at the same operating conditions with the temperature difference between initial and end thermal storage temperatures of approximately 18 K, the latent thermal storage provides higher discharged heat for 68% in comparison to the water-only thermal storage system.

Conclusions: The results from the present research showed that the inclusion of 37 % of PCM that is encapsulated in spherical modules led to 68 % higher thermal storage in comparison to the water-only system. This results showed that at the same operating conditions, thermal storage volume can be reduced by up to 68 % if PCMs are inserted inside the water thermal storage system. This provides increased energy density that is needed when integrating RES systems in retrofits of the buildings where space constrains represents a common issue. This means that there is not enough space to install a water thermal storage system, but there is a need to store a sufficient amount of heat or cold to level out the mismatch between the supply of RES and thermal demand of the building. This kind of latent thermal storage solution with spherically encapsulated PCM can be used for low-temperature applications with a smaller temperature difference in water heating and cooling systems. Besides the function of heat transfer fluid, the water also has a function of thermal storage medium what provides higher thermal power needed at the beginning of the discharge compared to some commercial solution of a compact latent thermal storage solution, where PCM represents around 90% of total volume. Furthermore, commercial solutions with integrated encapsulated PCMs operate at a higher temperature level and a bigger temperature difference.

References:

- [1] B.P Jelle, S.E. Kalnaes, Woodhead Publishing, 57-118 (2017).
- [2] RHC Platform, Brussels, (2012).
- [3] Z. He, X. Wang, X. Du, M. Amjad, L. Yang, C. Xu, Applied Thermal Engineering, 147, 188-197 (2019).
- [4] Z. Zhou, j. Liu, C. Wang, X. Huang, F. Gao, S. Zhang, B. Yu, Journal of Cleaner Production, 198, 1262-1275 (2018).
- [5] R. Koželj, E. Osterman, F. Leonforte, C. Del Pero, A. Miglioli, E. Zavrl, R. Stropnik, N. Aste, U. Stritih, Materials, 13, 2971-2993 (2020).